

NONMETALLIC CASTABLE TOOLING FOR ADVANCED COMPOSITE STRUCTURE

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A desire to minimize costs has been directed at the tooling associated with the fabrication of substructural elements of an advanced composite vertical stabilizer. These elements have a characteristic I-beam configuration with the web being either flat or sinewave. Tooling to fabricate these types of substructural elements had been developed and demonstrated on another program. However, it was believed that a concept could be developed which would provide tighter dimensional control thereby improving the quality of the finished part and reducing fabrication as well as assembly costs. A tooling concept taking advantage of the low-cost features of castable nonmetallic materials was developed for the curing of advanced composite parts. The development and implementation of tooling made of castable ceramic and elastomeric material is discussed.